

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

This issue presents seven high quality papers covering a variety of subjects from logic and classification to ontologies and linked data to information technology for educational support.

D. Gaina et al. from Japan report on their research of constructor-based logics, specifically on rules for the constructor-based Horn logics formalized as institutions. In a collaborative research from Saudi Arabia, Egypt and the USA T. F. Gharib, N. Badr, S. Haridy and A. Abraham introduce their research on the enhancement of ontology learning by a methodology for enriching lexical ontologies. R.J.M. Hartog et al. from The Netherlands report on the research of large-scale use of digital learning resources in higher education. Research on a linked open data approach in the e-science domain is reported by a research collaboration of A. Latif from Germany, M.T. Afzal from Pakistan and H. Maurer from Austria. M.-T. Martín-Valdivia et al. from Spain contribute with their research on sentiment classification, precisely on the effect of using neutral sample reviews found in an opinion corpus in order to improve a sentiment polarity classification system. J. Melero et al. from Spain give interesting insights of a study reviewing constructivist learning methods with supportive tools in ICT higher education.

The paper "The Educational Affordances of Widgets and Application stores" by D. Griffiths et al. was originally submitted to the J.UCS special issue on "Technology for Learning across Physical and Virtual Spaces". According to the guest editors Delgado Kloos et al. the submission was not at the center of the topic of the special issue. However, the reviewers stressed the high quality of the paper and recommended its publication in a regular issue. The paper represents a relevant contribution to the understanding of the pedagogical opportunities and challenges of interoperability specifications and related technological developments.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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